

Ride 2Rail

D6.5 EXPLOITATION STRATEGY

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The aim of this deliverable is to present an exploitation strategy developed for RIDE2RAIL project. The deliverable describes the tools used to exploit the solutions of the RIDE2RAIL project to stakeholders, to members of the project and to their partners. The tools described in the documents should facilitate exploitation.

The RIDE2RAIL exploitation strategy is addressed to a continuous project process, accompanying its activities since an early stage, and channelling all efforts towards high adoption levels and self-sustainability of the solution.

As a background on the project, RIDE2RAIL aims to develop an innovative framework for intelligent mobility solution and to promote an effective ride sharing practice of citizens, making it a complementary transport mode that extends public transport networks. To achieve the increased uptake of the RIDE2RAIL solutions by relevant stakeholders in Europe and beyond, an adequate engagement level with the above mentioned stakeholders is essential, together with project solutions widely disseminated to relevant target groups.

To reach an audience as wide as possible, WP6 leader, UITP, worked during and after the project end to encourage other associations and organisations in the consortium to further disseminate of the project solutions and knowledge developed by the consortium in the 41 months of RIDE2RAIL lifetime. Their expertise in European research projects, prominent status in the field of transportation and wide cross-sectorial network make them an important tool in making the exploitation of RIDE2RAIL a success.

Business Model Canvas (BMC) has been chosen in this document to establish exploitable project results, setting out specific business plans, identifying the projects benefits and target groups. The BMC then describes how project results can be exploited – commercially or otherwise – and potentially by whom. The potential revenue streams identified include advertising, selling of data, and subscription fees. One of the most important aspects remains promotion and dissemination of RIDE2RAIL solutions.

Abbreviations and acronyms

API	Application programming interface
BMC	Business Model Canvas
DC	Driver Companion
EU	European Union
GHG	Green House Gases
HSL	Helsinki Regional Transport Authority
IP4	Innovation Programme 4
ICT	Information and communications technology
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IT	Information technology
ITS	Intelligent Transport System
MaaS	Mobility as a Service
RP	Revealed Preference
S2R JU	Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking
SP	Stated Preference
TC	Travel Companion
TSP	Transport Service Provider
WP	Work Package

2. BACKGROUND

The present document constitutes the Deliverable D6.5 “Exploitation strategy” in the framework of the Task 6.4 of the project RIDE2RAIL.

3. OBJECTIVES/AIM

One of the RIDE2RAIL goals is to integrate multiple data sets and sources and existing transport platforms, and to integrate and harmonise real time and diverse information about rail, public transport, ride-sharing and crowdsourcing in a social ecosystem, testing it “on field” in the 4 demo locations (Athens, Helsinki, Brno, Padua). The project designs, develops and tests a set of software components, i.e. RIDE2RAIL solutions for the IP4 ecosystem (some developed within the RIDE2RAIL project and integrated in the existing S2R Travel Companion, others developed by S2R Call For Members project and provided to RIDE2RAIL partners. The project, as a combination of what internally develops and what provided by CFM projects (with whom strict collaboration was established from the very beginning) delivers a set of validated proof of concepts and business cases. These are described in this document, envisaging future mobility scenarios.

Main goals of the RIDE2RAIL exploitation strategy are to reach the following objectives:

- To create a set of business frameworks for the commercial exploitation of the RIDE2RAIL products, according to the European and worldwide market trends;
- To identify key stakeholders (industries, service providers, industrial or user associations, standardisation initiatives, etc.) to be taken into account or liaised with, because of their high potential impact to project solution exploitation;
- To develop the exploitation strategy providing recommendations for the continuous use of the project solution after its closure, identifying the required actions leading sustainable exploitation.

4. EXPLOITATION STRATEGY

RIDE2RAIL's overall objective is to develop an innovative framework for intelligent mobility, facilitating the efficient combination of flexible and scheduled transport services, thus enhancing the performance of the overall mobility system. This framework, consisting in a combined suite of travel offer classifications and software components, have been, over the project lifetime, integrated in the S2R ecosystem, together with existing collective and on-demand transport services, connecting, and reinforcing the mobility offer especially in rural and low-demand areas, in order to induct the access to high-capacity services (rail, bus and other public transport services) thanks to easy-to-use multimodal and integrated travel planning, booking, issuing and other features.

The exploitation strategy presented in this document provides the recommendations for the continuous use of the solutions after the end of the project. Furthermore, this strategy involves a set of business frameworks for the commercial exploitation for the RIDE2RAIL products. The described business models are expected to include a basic income generated by advertising, selling of data and know-how from the project, and offering premium features. It would be targeted at a wide range of potential customers from service providers to end users, in line with the goal to have the RIDE2RAIL outcomes applied by the widest possible audience.

This strategy identifies the required actions, to lead to sustainable exploitation plans. This especially means engagement with key stakeholders identified because of their high potential impact to project solution exploitation. To that end, RIDE2RAIL conducted a social media campaign and hosted events (demonstrations and workshops) to get the key stakeholders involved.

Commercialisation potential for RIDE2RAIL identifies a list of exploitable project outputs that can be used as a product or a service. The list is settled and updated as needed, according to the European and worldwide market trends throughout the project duration. This document broadly outlines their commercial potential and highlights the value of proposed solutions.

Table 1 – Identified business cases

EXISTING BARRIERS FOR RIDE SHARING	TRAVEL SCENARIOS	RIDE2RAIL BUSINESS CASES
Insufficient awareness of dedicated services	Cooperation between ride sharing and train operators	Cooperation with existing train operators and deployment of integrated ticketing schemes
Need for flexibility in scheduling to allow and cope with change in plans	Family routine	Network of trusted crowd-based TSPs according to predicted individual plans
Lack of trust and willingness to ride with strangers	Business Trips	Agreement ledger based on Blockchain technology defining specific travel paths and rating users
Uncertainty in reaching agreements on sharing costs	Millennials leisure & work	Provision of services classifying travel offers and exposing costs for Ride Sharing trips

RIDE2RAIL addresses the current challenges of identifying criteria for multimodal travel planning by addressing the mentioned existing barriers in Ride Sharing practice, developing travel scenarios and testing related business cases.

4.1. Commercialisation potential for the RIDE2RAIL

Commercialisation is the process of bringing new products or services to market. The broader act of commercialisation entails production, distribution, marketing, sales, customer support, and other key functions critical to achieving the commercial success of the new product or service.

Commercialisation potential for the RIDE2RAIL identified products is settled and updated as needed, according to the European and worldwide market trends throughout the project duration.

In the Deliverable 2.2, the market is explored and the recommendations for a successful integration of the ride-sharing concept in the Shift2Rail IP4 ecosystem are identified. Following activities are organised and conducted in the Deliverable 2.2 (available on RIDE2RAIL project website):

- State-of-the-art analysis of existing ride-sharing systems operating around the world;

- Thorough review of the legal frameworks relevant to ride-sharing in the European countries, in order for potential barriers of implementation to be identified;
- Definition of ride-sharing users and identification of their characteristics.

Commercialisation of the RIDE2RAIL solutions could be ensured by following channels and tools:

- Campaigns on social media;
- Press;
- Enhancing the liaison with practitioners and stakeholders;
- Enriched website;
- Submission of scientific papers to relevant journals and conferences,
- Presentation of solution and prototypes;
- Organisation of Stakeholders' workshops.

4.2. Exploitation plans

Each exploitable result must contain a business plan to try to shorten as much as possible the time-to-market of the project outputs. Very important parts in the exploitation strategy are also dissemination and communication tools and activities. Through these tools, the RIDE2RAIL solutions are disseminated to target groups.

4.2.1. Project solution

The project has developed exploitable concepts and solutions in its duration. With that come some general strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats:

Figure 1 - RIDE2RAIL SWOT

The following list describes the project’s solutions relevant to exploitation plans:

RIDE2RAIL delivers the conceptual model assessing the trip convenience based on several relevant dimensions, thus enhancing available IP4 ontologies to better reflect the actual trip categories, user preferences and choice criteria;

RIDE2RAIL develops, tests, and delivers a suite of as-a-service software components, by exploiting synergies of existing mobility offers that will be integrated into extended, multimodal transport networks without requiring ad-hoc customisations that hamper massive product uptakes;

RIDE2RAIL provides recommendations on future development, deployment, and replication to Shift2Rail IP4 with special regards to demand management strategies for collective transport systems;

RIDE2RAIL delivers a set of validated proof of concepts and business cases envisaging future mobility scenarios where advanced transport solution was seamlessly integrated into existing rail and other collective transport services.

4.2.2. Benefits of the project’s solutions

The results of RIDE2RAIL can provide many unique benefits and advantages to stakeholders, for example making user experience more seamless for end users, creating business opportunities for service providers, and giving local/national authorities better insights into transport trends, making planning easier.

Particular ways stakeholders can benefit from the project's solutions are that:

- RIDE2RAIL maximised the availability of mobility and behavioural data from different data sources and identified clusters of trip categories based not only on origin-destination itineraries, but also on both descriptive factors (travel time, cost, comfort, accessibility) and prescriptive factors (environmental aspects, traffic restrictions) that may influence travellers' choices;
- RIDE2RAIL synchronised and aggregated individual/spot mobility initiatives in structured, inclusive, and collective behaviours, connecting them to high-capacity transport services thanks to advanced journey planning, ride matching and influencing social features that will facilitate the access to multimodal itineraries and reduce reluctance to adopt sharing mobility practices;
- RIDE2RAIL enhanced carpooling diffusion, relying on widely-used communication channels, and contributed to a better understanding of the relevance of ride-sharing TSP complementary to rail and public transport in European urban and rural areas;
- RIDE2RAIL provided an open, connected, multimodal IT environment where innovative solution such as the Shift2Rail Travel Companion personal application and the RIDE2RAIL crowd-based TSPs are easily adopted by target user groups overcoming the existing barriers to user adoption;
- RIDE2RAIL demonstrated, validated, and evaluated user acceptance of its solution in 4 European sites (Padua, Brno, Athens and Helsinki) by deploying trial activities with real users and disseminating the achieved impacts in terms of user adoption and related improved transport performances;
- RIDE2RAIL analysed factors influencing users' decisions and related attitudes in "consuming" mobility according to emerging models and systems that could become the ground-breaking solution for currently unappealing rural areas.

4.2.3. Target groups

RIDE2RAIL develops a complete definition of the clustered trip categories, and it identified incentives that are provided to travellers in order to urge them to make more environmentally conscious and less congestion-burdening choices. More information about the incentives' conceptualisation is mentioned in the deliverables D2.1 First conceptualisation of choice criteria and incentives and D2.4 Final conceptualisation of choice criteria and incentives.

Identified actions and exploitation plans try to influence and address the related industries and end-users' customers.

Outputs could be used for the next exploitation in wide area by the following target groups:

- Public and private transport operators;

- National, local and regional authorities;
- City and transport planners;
- ICT suppliers and software developers;
- Retailers, travel agencies, distributors;
- MaaS providers;
- Payment service providers;
- International associations;
- Community groups;
- Regional, national, and European mobility clusters and industrial associations;
- Other networks and platforms;
- The academic community (researchers and students);
- Travellers.

4.2.4. Strategy

To encourage post-project use RIDE2RAIL solutions, the project focuses mainly on extensive dissemination and synergies. Nevertheless, project partners are engaged in several means to that end:

- **Dissemination, education, and awareness:** Workshops, seminars, and campaigns to promote the benefits of multimodal transport and raise awareness about the advantages of RIDE2RAIL's solutions. Collaborate with educational institutions involved in the project, industry associations, and local authorities to build awareness;
- **Stakeholder and end-user engagement and feedback:** Actively engage with stakeholders and end-users to gather feedback on RIDE2RAIL solutions, progress, and their experiences with RIDE2RAIL's services;
- **Continuing innovation:** Foster innovation based on RIDE2RAIL solutions within the RIDE2RAIL project and beyond. Continuously assess market trends and explore new features to promote possible follow-up solutions;
- **Business models and revenue streams:** Identify viable business models and revenue streams with the knowledge of products and services available on the market today. Monitor market trends for new business opportunities.

5. COMMERCIAL EXPLOITATION OF THE RIDE2RAIL SOLUTIONS

The purpose of this section is to define a suitable business model approach for a commercial service perspective to possibly deliver a service offering based on the value proposition of the RIDE2RAIL solutions.

5.1. Context

There is a growing recognition of the importance of multimodal transport systems that seamlessly integrate different modes of transport. Rail plays a crucial role in such systems, providing connectivity between urban centres, airports, and other hubs and acting as a backbone of the mobility system in urban and rural areas. There also is a growing focus on sustainability in the transport sector with rail transport generally being considered more environmentally friendly compared to other modes of transport. With RIDE2RAIL aimed to further enhance sustainability and efficiency of transport, it naturally fills that demand.

The project also leans heavily into digitalisation, including data analytics. These subject are heavily sought after by commercial subject at the time of the RIDE2RAIL development for their potential to increase efficiency, improve safety, and enable better reliability.

Naturally, passenger comfort, connectivity, personalisation, and expanding the scope of passengers are subjects that have been on the market ever since and whilst perhaps not as directly commercially exploitable, it can give an important edge to service providers.

5.2. Business model

The chosen approach is the Business Model Canvas (BMC) that it is recognised as an internationally standardised tool for innovative marketable solution. BMC will help to structure the correct business model, as it shows a graphical representation of all the important steps in a business model. It is structured into 9 blocks, all of them relevant to the solution considered: key partners, key activities, key resources, added value, user experience, channels, user segments, cost structure, revenue streams.

Figure 2 - Business Model Canvas

Partners were chosen because they are responsible for public service obligation ordering, operation, and economic effectiveness of public transport in their respective spheres. Service providers were chosen on geographic terms and their cooperation was sealed with a Letter of Support. Institutions and associations selected as partners are notoriously well known throughout the sector. Some heavily influence R&D activities, others influence European legislation, etc. The chapter 1.4 describes this in more detail.

Structure of **costs** is defined mostly by fulfilling the project’s potential as well as some operational costs inherent in providing a service through an app or web app.

As this is essentially an IT solution, the **resources** required by it are corresponding. A backbone of as-a-service components is required for the operation. However, the operation also should be under the umbrella of an organisation providing the public transport service as a whole.

The main **value** of RIDE2RAIL’s solution lies in deepening of multimodality, implementing of on-demand transport services and increasing public transport services performance, and therefore overall efficiency. Which should lead to cutting the number of single occupant trips. At the same time increased accessibility should among other things facilitate use of rural public transport, potentially to the point of creating “smart rural transport areas”.

The nature of the solution means that the **relation** with **customers** (transport service providers) would be a fairly standard software-as-a-service relationship between the software/service provider and the client.

Channels to reach the target audience are all the modern tools, as well as 1st party marketing and using websites of some key partners.

The **customer** base of the solution is diverse and layered, from end-users (travellers), who are going to be interacting with the apps, through association, to authorities and transport providers, who are necessary to provide transport to begin with

Key activities of the project and the solution include innovative approaches, such as using the Conceptual Data Model developed in another Shift2Rail project - LINX4RAIL. This, among other things, enables use of newly-developed solutions in IP4 of Shift2Rail/Europe's Rail. Interoperability Framework then allows transferability to other innovative services. The main activity of the developed solution lies in providing services like real-time route planning, ride matching, and other services linked to multimodal transport, and develop software to this goal. Experience from this project is used to provide recommendations for future development.

To secure multiple **revenue streams**, it is expected that the data a specific 3rd party applications can use are going to be charged for. The same applies to knowledge or know-how necessary for the development of additional tools within applications of service providers, etc. Also, common app-based income channels would be implemented, such as advertising and premium features. Because the project was not aimed to develop a commercial solution, it is expected that pricing and other financial specifics are going to be addressed during an actual implementation.

6. TARGET STAKEHOLDERS

The composition of the RIDE2RAIL consortium representing all stakeholders' groups, allows the implementation of specific measures for a more efficient connectivity and information sharing for the new business opportunities and innovative transport schemes. The European and international relevance of the RIDE2RAIL partners gives the right confidence that project's actions have an international impact, as summarised below by the potential exploitation intentions of the most relevant stakeholders.

6.1. Most relevant stakeholders

- **Local Authorities:** continuation to use the RIDE2RAIL solutions, both technical and business related, for a longer-term ride-sharing service development and incentives to change user behaviour;
- **Transport Service Providers:** direct benefits brought by the RIDE2RAIL project by having an integrated system which expands their potential users/customers. They also investigate possible additional services enforcing their business;
- **ICT/ITS suppliers/consultant companies, both part of RIDE2RAIL:** contributed to push interoperable and cost-efficient solution. The technical developments supported in the project widened ITS offering and experience that commercially exploited thereafter;
- **Research Institutes:** disseminated the solution from the different sites, in controlled as well as field conditions, to the academic community by presentations at national and international conferences and in academic journals;
- **Transport Association:** ensure the enlargement of the consensus base of the solution within their members. This happened through the capitalisation of the project solution into specific association activities and documentation like workshops dedicated to the project topics or the production of guidelines for members.

6.2. Stakeholders' engagement

As part of the exploitation strategy, stakeholders are engaged in multiple steps of the project. The exploitability of RIDE2RAIL solutions is ensured, by assuring consensus and concurrently practicality of the solution for the end users. WP6's Stakeholders Workshops acts as the interface for other WPs gathered input from external stakeholders in Europe. To organise the gathering of input from stakeholders, each WP defined its needs also by using information from workshops where stakeholders are invited to in order to provide feedback and other input for RIDE2RAIL. The stakeholders' workshops and engagement enhances the exploitability and credibility of the project solution by having a better understanding of the needs of the involved stakeholders, and thereby being able to tailor outputs to the users and contexts. Engagement is done, among others, through face-to-face (e.g. RIDE2RAIL's stakeholder workshops) as well as online stakeholder engagements formats (e.g. online

surveys). Through its consortium partners and in particular UITP, EURNEX, UNIFE and UIC, the RIDE2RAIL project has a unique access to working groups and commissions/Committees/Working Groups that provided input and exploited project solution.

PARTNERS' INTENT ON EXPLOITATION OF RESULTS

This chapter outlines RIDE2RAIL partners' strategies for making the most of the project's outcomes. It lays out the plans for exploitation of RIDE2RAIL results within the dynamic landscape of the transport sector by the diverse consortium and dedicated stakeholders.

Table 2 - CERTH exploitation strategy

CERTH		
Type	Result	Exploitation plan
Knowledge gained	Software development	CERTH will exploit the experience gained through the project in order to further expand the notion of ridesharing and MaaS in Greece, both from the research and actual operation perspective. The cooperation with major technological partners was a valuable experience; the Institute's network has been expanded and this will be exploited in the future through the forming of new consortia in order to participate in research projects
	Project participation	
Dissemination content/activities	Publications, website, ...	CERTH has already made a number of peer reviewed publications, as well participated in Conferences, announcing the Project's results and disseminating this way both the knowledge gained and the results achieved.

Table 3 – UNIZA exploitation strategy

UNIZA		
Type	Result	Exploitation plan
Software developed	Offer Categoriser	Used as examples in project-based teaching when explaining how to implement end points
	Offer Matcher & Ranker	
	Incentive Provider	UNIZA team gained knowledge of the evaluation framework and associated methodology, plus oversee the data collection process to take place in CZ/SK pilot site.
Knowledge gained	Software development	UNIZA team got a lot of experiences from the design of a methodology for assessing the quality of transport in the context of the PRM passengers and experiences with mapping the current and future demand for the traveller’s requirements, travel behaviour and mobility needs as well as in the analysis of legal aspects of ride-sharing in Slovakia/V4 countries. UNIZA team used all gained information and knowledge (in compliance with the project obligations, the GRANT and the Consortium Agreement) for upgrading teaching materials, application to the educational processes and possible future cooperation in field of transport science.
	Local demonstrations	Highly valued experiences and knowledge were obtain from testing TC and DC application and co-organization the Brno demonstration.
	Project participation	Used to demonstrate UNIZA capacity to participate in public transport related projects in other project applications. UNIZA as non-business organization used obtained knowledge for expansion of the portfolio of partners for future cooperation in scientific projects and educational processes.

Table 4 – METROPOLIA exploitation strategy

METROPOLIA		
Type	Result	Exploitation plan
Knowledge gained	Local demonstrations	Gained knowledge to be utilized in further projects
	Project participation	
Research data	Surveys, ...	To be used in education, more specifically in Metropolia’s course “Basics of Automated Mobility” (processes also smart mobility solutions in general)
Dissemination content/activities	Video about Agreement Ledger	The video has been uploaded on the Inlecom's website and YouTube account and has been shared in LinkedIn.

Table 5 – UITP exploitation strategy

UITP		
Type	Result	Exploitation plan
Dissemination content/activities	Publications, website, ...	UITP has a strong role in dissemination of the project through its extensive and international worldwide network, in order to keep R2R results well visible even after the project lifetime. UITP will make sure that dissemination of project results will be transferred to the sector and its members, through members’ newsletter, IT-TRANS, INNO-TRANS and the UITP Global Summit.
Outreach of the project	Promoting rail or public transport, continuing business or research relations, ...	RIDE2RAIL will help to bring new knowledge to the various activities interacting with the IT-ITS UITP Committee, Combined Mobility Platform, UITP Rail Committees and relative Working Groups, UITP Training programme and Transport Economics Committee to find synergies and to exchange knowledge on personal traveller information systems and trip tracking.

Table 6 - FIT exploitation strategy

FIT Consulting		
Type	Result	Exploitation plan
Knowledge gained	Project participation	FIT is a very active company in joining international projects initiatives. Each project contributes to add experience both in terms of project management and in terms of knowledge. FIT capitalizes this kind of experience to best perform in next market challenges.
Research data	Surveys, ...	Data collected and analysis will be part of the knowledge asset of the company. The R2R experience permitted to gain a deeper confidence how to spread mobility solutions to people.
Outreach of the project	Promoting rail or public transport, continuing business or research relations, ...	FIT is a leading company in mobility consultancy, every experience gained on the field is exploited to best fit solutions for our customers.

Table 7 - UNIFE exploitation strategy

UNIFE		
Type	Result	Exploitation plan
Dissemination content/activities	Publications, website, ...	UNIFE will make sure that the outcomes of the RIDE2RAIL project are disseminated to the widest possible outreach based on its membership and overall network, both within UNIFE committees and working groups and among UNIFE members and contacts.
Outreach of the project	Promoting rail or public transport, continuing business or research relations, ...	UNIFE disseminated the results of Ride2Rail through its Technical Platform bringing together all UNIFE members' CTOs (or equivalent) and internal Working Groups, raising awareness of the relevance of the outcomes of the projects among its members and promoting the continuation of the work done in Ride2Rail in future R&D activities.

Table 8 - POLIMI exploitation strategy

POLIMI		
Type	Result	Exploitation plan
Software developed	Travel Service Provider	As part of the Travel Service Provider, Politecnico developed the Trip Tracking mechanism. Politecnico intends to exploit the piece of software developed in future mobility projects, and also for further academic research (theses, etc.) and dissemination
	Offer Matcher & Ranker	Politecnico developed the THOR core of the Offer Matcher and Ranker. THOR will be exploited for research purposes, both in future projects, and also in academic courses and thesis works.
Knowledge gained	Software development	The development of the two piece of software improved the knowledge of Politecnico's researchers in developing user-centered mobility solutions.
Dissemination content/activities	Publications, website, ...	The Trip Tracker and THOR have been disseminated through various academic channels, and in particular journals and conferences.

Table 9 - EURNEX exploitation strategy

EURNEX		
Type	Result	Exploitation plan
Knowledge gained	Software development	To use the knowledge gained for the coordination of future projects in the transport sphere
	Project participation	To participate in consortia for future proposals related to multimodality in both freight and passenger
Dissemination content/activities	Publications, website, ...	To become familiar with new dissemination tools (e.g. Zenodo)
Outreach of the project	Promoting rail or public transport, continuing business or research relations, ...	Attract attention to Eurnex to gain new members for the association

Table 10 – INLECOM exploitation strategy

INLECOM		
Type	Result	Exploitation plan
Software developed	Agreement Ledger	Parts of the Agreements ledger module, such as the Ricardian contract generator is being used in an in-house blockchain solution that supports use cases from other projects.
Knowledge gained	Software development	Inlecom's engineers gained valuable experience in developing blockchain applications. Inlecom leverages this expertise for the design and development of other solutions in the context of EC funded projects. Moreover, the expertise is employed for the development of successful EC funded proposals.

Table 11 – OLTIS exploitation strategy

OLTIS Group		
Type	Result	Exploitation plan
Knowledge gained	Local demonstrations	Further develop and enhance the use of ride sharing platforms in towns such as Brno, Liberec etc., in the Czech Republic.
	Project participation	Take advantage of the experience gained in the framework of the project and use it to participate in other similar research projects and/or studies

Table 12 - CEFRIEL exploitation strategy

CEFRIEL		
Type	Result	Exploitation plan
Software developed	Agreement Ledger	The agreements ontology (https://ride2rail.github.io/agreement-ledger-ontology/docs/terms/index.html) will be used in the context of TEADAL EU project to keep track of the data sharing agreements between companies.
	Offer Categoriser	The acquired knowledge of the TRIAS specifications is being reused in other EU projects dealing with interoperability and data sharing in the transportation domain.
Knowledge gained	Software development	The participation to the development of the Offer categoriser allowed Cefriel to acquire knowledge about implementing microservices architecture using the Python language. Such knowledge will be reused in future consultancy and research projects.
Research data	Surveys, ...	The survey named "Study of travellers' preferences towards travel offer categories and incentives in the journey planning context" (https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0284844) allowed Cefriel to have a better understanding of the travellers' behaviour, and it provided valuable domain knowledge which will be used in the context of consultancy and EU projects targeting mobility.
Dissemination content/activities	Publications, website, ...	Cefriel's participation to conferences and to Shift2Rail dissemination events contributed to improve the visibility of the company as a technological partner in the digitalisation of the transportation and mobility domain.

Table 13 – ELLINIKO METRO (previously AMETRO) exploitation strategy

ELLINIKO METRO (previously AMETRO)		
Type	Result	Exploitation plan
Knowledge gained	Local demonstrations	Stated preference survey at two metro stations used for recruitment purposes for local demonstrations
Research data	Surveys, ...	Through the Stated Preference survey which was conducted during the project, data on metro user preferences regarding travel behaviour and attitudes towards ride sharing were collected.
Dissemination content/activities	Publications, website, ...	Through the SP survey a large number of metro users were informed about Ride2Rail project Ride2Rail Presentation at International conference in Athens Paper accepted for publication, on Multimodal Traveling with Rail and Ride-sharing: Lessons Learned

Table 14 – EURECAT exploitation strategy

EURECAT		
Type	Result	Exploitation plan
Software developed	Driver Companion	The software components developed during the Ride2Rail project can offer a reference implementation for their respective functionalities. The availability of these components can foster partnerships for the next generation of integrated mobility solutions. The components are thoroughly documented, with the deliverable provide ample details from the conception to the implementation phase, ensuring easy adoption and adaptation for future initiatives. In particular, the Offer Categoriser, Offer Matcher and Ranker and Incentive Provider use state-of-the-art solutions that will be further developed. The Offer Categoriser and Offer Matcher and Ranker are designed in a modular way and are suitable for projects that need to manage,
	Travel Service Provider	
	Agreement Ledger	
	Offer Categoriser	
	Offer Matcher & Ranker	
	Incentive Provider	

		categorize, and rank a large volume of transport-related offers.
Knowledge gained	Software development	<p>The knowledge gained by the WP3 partners relates to the development of a system with a modular architecture, which leverages microservices in the form of Docker containers, which communicate with each other through the HTTPS protocol. The benefit of this architecture is precisely modularity which provides several advantages: efficiency, scalability, redundancy.</p> <p>Most importantly, these architecture has provided ease of development allowing us to divide the development work among the partners of the various WP3 tasks. In particular, each of the microservices that compute the various features that are used by the Offer Categorizer and Offer Matcher and Ranker were developed independently.</p>

7. RIDE2RAIL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION TOOLS & ACTIVITIES

The RIDE2RAIL project aims to develop an innovative framework for intelligent mobility solutions and to promote an effective ride sharing practice of citizens. To achieve the increased uptake of RIDE2RAIL solutions by relevant stakeholders in Europe and beyond, it is essential to ensure sufficient engagement with all stakeholders and progress/results are widely disseminated to relevant target groups. This has been done by focussing on various aspects:

- Establishing RIDE2RAIL as a brand while disseminating project objectives, raise awareness on topic of ride-sharing and public transport, generate interest through various channels including project website, brochure, press articles, animation video, newsletters;
- Active involvement of local practitioners and stakeholders: dissemination of demos and their objectives/set-up on website and social media, heavily utilising partners' networks for this. Local dissemination has played an important part in RIDE2RAIL seeing demo audiences were to be targeted locally, in local languages;
- Promote the findings of the project, promote the exploitation of the RIDE2RAIL innovations: through events (both organisation and participation) website, scientific publications, social media articles, newsletters, UITP Project Brief, final leaflet, and other.

7.1. Visual identity

To establish the RIDE2RAIL project as a consistent and strong brand, a full visual identity was created at the start of the project, including a logo, visual charter (colour scheme, fonts), and document templates. A solid identity increases engagement and recognition among the public and has been an essential part of the dissemination strategy.

7.1.1. RIDE2RAIL logo, symbol & visual identity

The RIDE2RAIL logo was developed in February 2020. Project logo and symbol were developed to support project visual identity.

Figure 3 - RIDE2RAIL logo

Figure 4 - RIDE2RAIL symbol

To ensure consistent use of the RIDE2RAIL logo and colours, various templates have been developed: a PowerPoint template, a deliverable template, a meeting minutes template, and a meeting agenda template. All consortium partners are encouraged to make use of these templates when presenting the RIDE2RAIL project in internal or external meetings.

To further support the project identity, a full graphic character has been developed, consisting of the project colours and fonts. It also includes various other visuals, such as a banner and background, which can be used in the different dissemination tools, such as the project newsletters.

7.1.2. Project roll-up

The project roll-up was created as another means to strengthen the RIDE2RAIL identity and to be used at events.

Figure 5 - RIDE2RAIL roll-up

7.2. RIDE2RAIL leaflets

7.2.1. Project leaflet

The first RIDE2RAIL leaflet has been produced at the beginning the project, to describe understandably the project background, approach, objectives, and scope. More specifically, it lists the project duration, the consortium partners, the EU funding, and the project website and contacts.

The leaflet is publicly available via the RIDE2RAIL website and has been distributed at events RIDE2RAIL has taken part in. The leaflet has been printed and distributed more than 100 times. Due to the COVID-19 crisis, distribution of the leaflet (in particular at project start) has happened mainly digitally.

7.2.1. Final project leaflet

In addition to the project leaflet produced at the start of the project, the final leaflet was created in the final month of the RIDE2RAIL project to highlight achievements of the project, focusing in particular on demo results.

The final project leaflet is distributed through the website, social media channels and partners' networks. Of course, this document (combined to leaflet 1) can serve long after project completion as a short summary of the RIDE2RAIL project and its solution.

The leaflet is available through this link: <https://ride2rail.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/FINAL-LEAFLET.pdf>.

When it comes to the final factsheet, it is under preparation (at the time of writing this deliverable).

7.3. RIDE2RAIL website

The RIDE2RAIL website can be accessed via <http://www.ride2rail.eu/>. It has been the main communication tool for the consortium partners, relevant stakeholders, and the public. It was launched in March 2020 and has been one of the most important means to disseminate the project to a wider audience and to recap all project main activities. The website has a dedicated section where all relevant project news are listed. Public deliverable are uploaded on the website once officially accepted.

Figure 6 - RIDE2RAIL website homepage

7.4. RIDE2RAIL on social media

Social media are an established method to increase visibility and outreach and have been central to the RIDE2RAIL dissemination efforts. Social media offer a great opportunity to open the dialogue with the public, enabling direct interaction and raising awareness of the public towards the RIDE2RAIL project. Therefore the project's own social accounts were (Twitter, LinkedIn) founded.

7.5. RIDE2RAIL Newsletter

The RIDE2RAIL e-newsletter has been created to inform subscribers about the developments of the project and the most interesting events or happenings. It hosts project news, demo progresses and results, interviews with Europe's Rail and demo leaders/key project partners. Timing for the release has been flexible, as this always depended on the evolution of the project and content produced.

Throughout the project's lifetime, 4 official RIDE2RAIL E-newsletters have been sent out.

7.6. Video

Two videos have been produced within RIDE2RAIL Project Lifetime: one from the project partner INLECOM, mainly targeted at showing the WP3 features and in particular the Agreement Ledger; one from the coordinator UITP to be used as a dissemination tool to promote the project on a wider scale.

Links to videos are here:

INLECOM Video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NryzSH57iZs>

UITP Video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bsPP-6pP2Ho1>

7.7. Papers and publications

RIDE2RAIL partners have published numerous articles and papers in scientific journals as well as at conferences throughout the project's duration. The complete list of publications can be found in the Technical Periodic Reports.

7.8. Dissemination activities via partners

The dissemination of RIDE2RAIL through partners' channels has been of the essence in the overall dissemination strategy. Most of the RIDE2RAIL partners participate in important networks of operators and universities, alongside engineering groups and specialists. With the aim of widening the dissemination of the project, UITP has encouraged the partners to use these networks to spread information about project activities and solution and to act as so-called 'Ambassadors' of the project.

7.9. Local demonstrations

Local demonstration events were organised in all demo sites locally in order to present their demonstration case and/or related solution. These events attracted press coverage and informed the local citizens and stakeholders. They were organised by the demo leaders under the supervision of UITP. UITP ensured homogeneity of these events, while the partners represented the demos. These events brought visibility to the RIDE2RAIL consortium and the Shift2Rail JU towards local stakeholders and end users, while promoting the services and tools available in each city to encourage sustainable travel options.

Showcasing practical application of the project's innovations, technologies, and engaging with stakeholders was in part conducted with the aim to expand exploitation opportunities as well as to gather feedback to that end.

Local demonstrations are summarily described in the Final Summary Report of the Project (D1.4) and more in detail in WP4 deliverables.

7.10. Events

Events play an important role within the RIDE2RAIL dissemination activities, as they provides an excellent opportunity to promote the project results to a more diverse audience

other than those reached by dissemination means such as the website, social media, and the leaflet.

The project consortium hosted several events as part of promotion and dissemination activities. These included demonstration events, workshops, and the final event. Partners also highlighted the project on international conferences and exhibitions.

The complete list of events can be found in the Periodic Technical Reports.

8. IPR ASPECTS

In general, tools, methodology documents, benchmarks and case studies are available to all, and knowledge is governed in accordance with the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. Some proprietary training content and tools developed by the partners may be available at the discretion and terms of their respective owner. As per HORIZON 2020 and Shift2Rail JU obligations and recommendations, the project was largely developed in as open access. This was done by means of a public GitHub git where most of the technical deliverables are available. The project's website (ride2rail.eu) also includes freely available deliverables in the library section. As such, the project outputs are widely accessible to the general public for educative or scientific, exploitation (use, copying, modification and/or distribution) to facilitate wide adoption of project results.

Many of them are publicly available on the project's GitHub - <https://github.com/Ride2Rail> - as well as on Zenodo - <https://zenodo.org/communities/ride2rail/>.

Specifics of access rights and exploitation possibilities are governed not only by both the Consortium Agreement and in case of exploitation also by the Grant Agreement, but also by the RIDE2RAIL's IPR Directory, as set out in 2.2.6 of the Grant Agreement.

9. CONCLUSION

One of the most important point of the exploitation strategy is present, promote and highlight the solution of the RIDE2RAIL project and its future use. In general, the RIDE2RAIL solutions will serve for further research activities on intramodality, technologies and Shift2Rail IP4 and also for papers and publications which will have an impact at global level (solution presented in conferences, events, meetings etc.).

The partners involved in the RIDE2RAIL project operate in various areas of the transport segment which allows to exploit the RIDE2RAIL solutions by many options. For this reason, many actions were identified for exploitation. These actions will continue after the completion of the project and through these actions will be ensured maximal exploitation of the RIDE2RAIL solutions. For example, the partners will promote and raise awareness of relevance of the solutions in future research and development activities. Moreover, the partners have a unique access to working groups and commissions that can help to attract stakeholders and wide audience. The exploitation will be ensured also by the engineering software components and bringing them into the market.

The solution will also be disseminated within universities and educational environment through academic publications in journals or international conferences. The solution will be exploited to expand academic horizon for students and build on existing expertise in the fields of mobility planning, transport organisation, as well as optimisation of algorithms for shared mobility and mass transit. The RIDE2RAIL solutions will help to educate students in new relevant technologies that will help them in achieving their career goals, academic and industrial.

REFERENCES

KLENTON W. (2020). *Commercialization*. Retrieved from <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/c/commercialization.asp>

RIDE2RAIL. (2020). *Amendment number 881825-3*

RIDE2RAIL. (2020). *Deliverable D2.1 - First conceptualization of choice criteria and incentives*. Retrieved from <https://RIDE2RAIL.eu/resources-library/>

RIDE2RAIL. (2020). *Deliverable D2.2 - State-of-the-art of ridesharing in target EU countries*. Retrieved from <https://RIDE2RAIL.eu/resources-library/>

RIDE2RAIL. (2021). *Deliverable D2.4 - Final conceptualization of choice criteria and incentives*. Retrieved from <https://RIDE2RAIL.eu/resources-library/>